

Problems Encountered by the Grade 2 Teachers in the Division of Dumaguete City in Teaching Mathematics Using Mother Tongue: A Basis For An Action Plan

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Abstract

The study aimed to identify the problems encountered by Grade 1 Mathematics teachers in teaching Mathematics using the Mother Tongue as a medium of instruction in the schools of Division of Dumaguete City and their relationship to class academic performance of the pupils.

The survey was descriptive and correlational in nature. It utilized frequency distribution, percentage, mean, weighted mean, and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient.

Majority of the teachers are non-master's degree holders and have been in the teaching profession for a longer time. Most of them attended the indicated seminar-workshops related to the K-12 instruction. The teachers encountered a "serious" problem in the translation of Mathematical concepts or language in the Mother tongue and had a "moderate" problem in the utilization of effective questioning skill and in giving of exercises and activities. Moreover, they faced a "slight" problem in the utilization of effective reacting technique.

The findings disclosed that the class academic performance of the pupils is in the "approaching proficiency" level. There is a "slight" negative relationship between the extent of problems encountered by the teachers in the translation of the Mathematical concepts and the class academic performance of the pupils. There is also a "slight" negative relationship between the number of relevant trainings attended by the teachers and the following variables: utilization of effective questioning skill, utilization of effective reacting technique and giving exercises and activities.

Moreover, the study showed that there is a "slight" negative relationship between the educational attainment of the teachers and the following variables: utilization of effective reacting technique and giving of exercises and activities.

It is, therefore, recommended that:

1. Teachers upgrade their skills in managing classroom instruction by pursuing further studies and attend more training focusing on the translation of the content of the Mathematics competencies in the Mother tongue.
2. Teachers, in coordination with the School Head, Public Schools District Supervisor, and Education Program Supervisor for Mathematics, formulate varied exercises activities in the Mother Tongue so as to enhance learning.

Keywords: *Mother Tongue, Translation of Mathematical Concepts, Question and Reaction Technique*

I. INTRODUCTION

Mathematics is one subject that pervades life at any age. Thus, its value goes beyond the classroom and the school. Mathematics as a school subject, therefore, must be learned comprehensively and with much depth. (K to 12 Curriculum Guide)

Teaching Mathematics in the primary level like any other school subject must be done using a language best understood by the recipients if the basic concepts, principles and laws of mathematics are to be meaningful to the children. This is so because language has always been vital in the effective transfer of learning. Thus, the medium of instruction often plays a fundamental role in the success of the teaching – learning process (Charanchi).

With the implementation of the K-12 Basic Education Curriculum, mother tongue is used as the medium of instruction in teaching Mathematics from Kindergarten to Grade III. Researchers believed that the level of development of children's mother tongue is a strong predictor of their second language development (Cummins). Abiri stated that Mathematics taught in a child's mother tongue has a lot of advantages, such as overcoming limited knowledge of foreign mathematical vocabulary. Teaching in the mother tongue also bring children closer to mathematics example and concepts, it helps the children to develop a mathematical vocabulary in the mother tongue. It equally helps adults who are not literate in English to understand and appreciate Mathematics.

Mathematical language is the collection of signs or symbols, abbreviations, axioms, method, formulae, and units that are necessary in mathematics teaching and learning. Understanding of its usage is imperative and cannot be underestimated. Obodo affirmed that failure of the learner to master the mathematical language lead to poor performance in the subject. The uniqueness of mathematics language has distinguished mathematics from other subjects. Anyone that cannot cope with imperial and native language which is based on verbal reasoning may likely get lost in quantitative reasoning where the use of mathematical language is necessary. Spatial and mathematical reasoning will help pupils to generate, retain, retrieve and transform well-structured visual images into mathematical appreciation with the aid of mathematical language (Lohman).

In the same vein, the teacher is the key factor in the success of any educational endeavour at all levels and in the realization of the objectives of the K-12 Basic Education curriculum. The world is becoming more complex with increase in mathematical advancement. This complex knowledge creates new expectations in teaching. To help learners master more challenging contents, teachers must go far beyond dispensing information, giving test and giving a grade. They must themselves know their subject areas deeply and they must understand how pupils think if they are to create experiences that actually work to produce (Darling-Hammond).

Several researches have been made about the perceived effectiveness of the use of mother tongue in the performance of pupils in any subject area but no study has been made on the translation of mathematics vocabulary or concepts in mother tongue and teachers effective questioning and reacting technique. It is on this premise that the researcher would like to know the problems encountered by the Grade 1 teachers in the Division of Dumaguete City in their third year of implementation in teaching mathematics using the mother tongue which is Sinugbuanong Binisaya in terms of mathematics vocabulary in mother tongue, and the academic performance of pupils so that proper intervention will be given and problems encountered will be addressed.

II. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research utilized the descriptive-correlational method. It is descriptive since it identified the problems encountered by the Grade 1 teachers in teaching Mathematics using mother and correlational since these problems will be correlated to the pupils' academic performance. Likewise, the relationship between the profile of the teachers and their problems was also identified.

Research Environment

The place of the study is Dumaguete City, which is known to be "The City of Gentle People". It is also known as the "University Town" since the place has a number of universities where students from different regions enroll and pursue their dreams.

The Division of Dumaguete City is composed of 18 public elementary schools coming from the three districts namely Dumaguete City West, South and North.

Research Respondents

The respondents of the study were the 56 Grade 1 teachers of the Division of Dumaguete City.

Research Instruments

The study made use of a questionnaire and pupils' average final rating in Mathematics during the school year 2013-2014. In Parts A and D, the researcher used the self-made questions. These questions were based on the feedback of the teachers on their problems encountered in translation of the mathematical concepts/language and giving of exercises during class observations and conference. The researcher also read articles and publications regarding mother tongue –based instruction and integrated important items in the questionnaire.

For Parts B and C, the researcher used a questionnaire made by SEAMEO INNOTECH entitled "The Interactive Instruction Series for Teacher Education, Trainor's Manual on the Art of Questioning and Reacting Techniques". SEAMEO INNOTECH is principally dedicated to identifying common and unique education problems and needs of Southeast Asian countries and developing innovative and technology-based solutions to address these problems. The Center aids in educational development within and outside the region through training and human resource development, research and evaluation, information and communications technology and other special programs addressing specific areas of concern in the Southeast Asian educational scenario.

The researcher asked permission that their instrument will be used in this study. The questionnaire was presented to three experts in the field of mathematics and in the use of mother as a medium of instruction for content validity. The suggestions of the three experts were considered. Then a dry run was conducted to 30 teachers to find out if the items were valid.

Research Data Gathering Procedure

After the design hearing, the researcher integrated all the comments and suggestions of the panel members. The validation of the questionnaire followed and finalized after the test and re-test procedure.

The researcher made a letter request for the distribution of the final questionnaire which was signed by the dean of the graduate school and approved by the Schools Division Superintendent in the Division of Dumaguete City. The endorsement and approved letter from the Schools Division Superintendent together with a letter request was presented to the principals of the respondents for formal permission

regarding the questionnaire to be distributed. During the distribution, the researcher personally explained to the respondents the purpose of the research. The questionnaires were retrieved after the respondents have answered the questions.

The Mathematics grades of the pupils were gathered with the permission of the principal.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the result of the study and provides in-depth analysis and interpretation of data.

Table 1. Profile of the Teachers in Terms of Their Educational Attainment and Number of years in Teaching Mathematics
n=56

Variables	Frequency	Percent (%)
<i>Educational Attainment</i>		
Bachelor’s Degree	20	35.71
With Master’s Degree Units	34	60.71
With Master’s Degree	2	3.58
<i>Number of Years in Teaching Mathematics</i>		
1 – 5 years	12	21.43
6 – 10 years	12	21.43
11 – 15 years	9	16.07
16 years and beyond	23	41.07

Table 1 shows that majority of the teachers are with master’s degree units and only 2 out of 56 or 3.58% have master’s degree while 35.71% have bachelor’s degree. The findings show that most of the teachers pursue further studies to improve one’s craft and acquire knowledge for one’s professional growth so as to enhance teaching capabilities. As the study of Charanchi revealed that there was a significant difference between the performance of pupils taught by teachers with higher qualification like a master’s degree compared to those pupils taught by teachers with lower qualification like bachelor’s degree. Oguntebi said the problem lies on the quality of Mathematics teachers and he further said, “for a teacher to teach Mathematics better he must also the subject better.

Other data in table 1 reveals the profile of teachers in terms of the number of years in teaching mathematics. Findings show that most of the teachers have 16 years and beyond experience in teaching Mathematics. Teaching experience of 1-5 years and 6 -10 years has the same percentage of 21.43% while 16.07% of the teachers have 11-15 years in teaching Mathematics. A bigger percentage of the teachers might but have vast experiences in teaching Mathematics but since this is the third year in the implementation of the K-12 program wherein Mother Tongue is used as the medium of instruction in teaching Mathematics most of them are still greenhorns.

It is said that, experience is the best teacher. Every teacher brings in the classroom his teaching experiences which could positively or adversely affect classroom interaction.

Moreover, teacher quality comes from good preparation in subject content as well as pedagogy, but preparation is only one part. Experience counts. Good students come from classes whose teachers have more years of teaching experience.

Table 2. Profile of the Teachers in Terms of Relevant Trainings Attended Related to K - 12
n=56

Seminar-Workshop/Activities	f	Yes (%)	Number of Times (Average)
1. Mass Training of Teachers on K-12 curriculum	54	96.43	Once
2. Mother Tongue as a Medium of Instruction	48	85.71	Once
3. Teaching Strategies for Mother Tongue Instruction	46	82.14	Once
4. Framework of the K-12 Program	49	87.50	Once

Table 2 illustrates the profile of teachers in terms of relevant trainings attended related to K-12. Most of the teachers attended the mass training of teachers on K-12 curriculum with 96.43%, framework of the K- 12 program with 87.50 %, mother tongue as a medium of instruction with 85.71% and 82.14% attended the teaching strategies for mother tongue instruction. All these trainings were attended by the teachers once.

The findings in Table 2 indicates that most of the teachers underwent training relevant to K-12 but it is very limited. Charanchi stressed that continuous training and mastery of the subject is an absolute necessity for effective teaching. The level of information possessed by the teacher should be much higher than that of the information he is expected to impart. Professional training will enable a person to acquire certain commendable characteristics such as adaptability, efficiency, the knack of arousing interest, command of instructional material and ability to face the class with confidence.

As cited by Gregorio, it is not sufficient to be a graduate at a Teacher Education Institution (TEI) or a college, or to stand high in the profession of teaching. Like the pupils, the teacher must grow, and this growth could be attained by attending professional training and pursuing further studies.

Felipe also affirms that trainings and seminars should be conducted to improve and develop the craft of each mentor in school. Teachers should be updated on modern instructional devices and learn new methods and techniques in teachings to prepare them in globalization (34).

Furthermore, Zulueta, et.al pointed out that training provides instruction in any organizational setting and was found to have an important role in enhancing the productivity of employees. Training has been a common term in any organization. When an employee’s performance is not satisfactory based on the organization’s standard, he needs training. Whenever the output-input within a time period of work is not met, the supervisor will readily say they lack training (81).

Table 3. Extent of Teachers’ Problems in Translation of Mathematical Concepts/Language

Extent of Problems in Translating significant mathematical terms in Mother Tongue in the following competencies:	\bar{w}_x	Verbal Equivalent
1. Composes and decomposes a given number – 4 ug 5, 5 ug 4, 6 ug 3	3.13	Moderate
2. Reads and writes numbers up to 100 in symbols and in words Ex.31 - <i>trayenta i-uno</i>	4.20	Serious
3. Renames numbers into tens and ones Ex. 78 – <i>7 tagnapulo 8 tinagus-a</i>	3.23	Moderate
4. Recognizes and compares coins and bills up to PhP100 and their notations Ex. 5 <i>kasingkopisosugbayentepisos</i>	3.66	Serious
5. Visualizes and adds numbers with sums through 99 without or with regrouping Ex. 25+47	3.41	Serious
6. Uses the expanded form to explain subtraction with regrouping 50 + 4 Ex. - $\underline{28 + 8}$	3.43	Serious
7. Counts groups of equal quantity using concrete objects up to 50 and writes an equivalent expression. Ex. 2 <i>groups of 5</i>	3.23	Moderate
8. Compares and classifies 2-dimensional (flat/plane) and 3 dimensional(solid) figures according to common attributes Ex. <i>Nawongsakono, rectangular ngakarton, cylindrical</i>	3.59	Serious
9. Constructs equivalent number expression using addition and subtraction. Ex. 6+5 = 12 -1	3.48	Serious
10. Estimate and measure capacity using non-standard unit Ex. <i>Si Nene nagkinahanglanug 30 kabasosa juice alangsayangnatawhan. angusakapitselmosulodug 5 kabasonga juice, pila man kapitselsa , angiyangandamon.</i>	3.50	Serious
11. Solves problems involving time. Ex. <i>Ika-walokataknaugnapulog lima</i>	4.13	Serious
12. Infers and interprets data presented in a pictograph without scales Ex. <i>Unsakabahinang pictograph?</i>	3.39	Serious
Composite Mean	3.53	Serious

Table 3 presents the extent of teacher’s problems in translation of Mathematical concepts/ language. 75% of the listed competencies were found to be a serious problem. Most of the teachers had a serious problem in the following competencies; reading and writing numbers up to 100 in symbols and in words; solving problems involving time; recognizing and comparing coins and bills up to PhP100 and their notations; comparing and classifying 2-dimensional (flat/plane) and 3 dimensional (solid) figures according to common attributes; constructing equivalent number expression using addition and subtraction; using the expanded form to explain subtraction with regrouping; visualizing and adding numbers with sums through 99 without or with regrouping; inferring and interpreting data presented in a pictograph without scales and estimating and measuring capacity using non-standard unit . The table also shows that 25% or 3 out 9 competencies are considered moderate in terms of translating these competencies in mother tongue.

Though contents are easy to teach but translating it to Sinugbuanong Binisaya is difficult because of the limited knowledge of the teachers in the mother tongue vocabulary. In the training conducted, there was no

particular session that focuses on the content of the lesson but more emphasis was given on the strategies and materials.

There is some special vocabulary in Mathematics according to Raborn. Mathematics vocabulary is said to be precise but not always familiar. Thompson and Rubenstein say that pupils need to master this mathematics language if they are to read, understand and discuss mathematical ideas. Unlike common English and our mother tongue, which pupils hear, see and use daily in reading, watching television and elsewhere, the language of Mathematics is limited to school.

Table 4. Extent of Teachers’ Problems in the Utilization of Effective Questioning Skill

Indicators	$\bar{w\bar{x}}$	Verbal Equivalent
1. Ability to ask varied type of question	3.00	Moderate
2. Ability to direct the question to all pupils.	2.63	Moderate
3. Ability to call on non-volunteer pupils.	2.68	Moderate
4. Ability to rephrase questions that are unclear to the pupils.	2.46	Moderate
5. Ability to ask related questions one from simple to complex one another.	2.77	Moderate
6. Ability to ask questions that require abstract thinking.	2.96	Moderate
7. Ability to ask questions that develop higher order thinking skills.	3.02	Moderate
8. Ability to provide for sufficient wait time for the pupils to answer.	2.84	Moderate
9. Ability to assess Comprehension	2.96	Moderate
10. Ability to involve in the discussion as many pupils as possible	2.63	Moderate
Composite Mean	2.79	Moderate

The table above reveals the extent of teacher’s problems in the utilization of effective questioning skill. Majority of the listed indicators were considered as a moderate problem. These results indicate that teachers have fully developed their art of questioning regardless of the medium of instruction used whether English or Mother Tongue but the content /concepts that will be asked hinder the teachers ability to ask effective and divergent questions.

Effective questioning techniques is one of the important methods to use to increase class participation and enhance pupils learning experiences.

Table 5. Extent of Teachers’ Problems in the Utilization of Effective Reacting Technique

Indicators	$\bar{w\bar{x}}$	Verbal Equivalent
1. Ability to provide feedback on the correctness or incorrectness of a response	2.71	Moderate
2. Ability to give appropriate praise to high quality responses	2.54	Slight
3. Ability to make follow up questions	2.39	Slight
4. Ability to redirect questions to other pupils	2.44	Slight
5. Ability to follow up a pupil’s response with related question	2.41	Slight
6. Ability to re-phrasing the seemingly unclear question	2.50	Slight
7. Ability to show non – verbal encouragement	2.52	Slight
8. Ability to encourage learners to ask questions	2.50	Slight
Composite Mean	2.50	Slight

Table 5 discloses the extent of teacher’s problems in the utilization of effective reacting technique. It reveals that a bigger percentage or 87.5% of the listed indicators are considered slight problem. The ability to provide feedback on the correctness or incorrectness of a response is a moderate problem. This means that teachers have developed the skill in handling pupils’ responses to the questions asked. According to Corpuz, the teacher’s reaction to the student’s inquisitiveness can motivate or demotivate students from asking more questions. Handling pupil’s response is crucial. By the way a teacher handles student’s responses; he either encourages or discourages them from actively participating in class interaction. Thus in providing corrective feedback, the teacher should give a hint or break down the question if necessary, to guide the learner to the correct response or the teacher may explain the correct answer when the learners cannot arrive at it.

Table 6. Extent of Teachers’ Problems in Giving Exercises and Activities

Indicators	$\bar{w\bar{x}}$	Verbal Equivalent
1. Availability of learning guides and other references	3.77	Serious
2. Varied activities prepared that will address diverse learners	3.39	Moderate
3. Availability of manipulative materials and other supplies	3.48	Serious
4. Fluency in the use of the mother tongue	2.80	Moderate
5. Mastery of the standards and competencies	2.80	Moderate
Composite Mean	3.25	Moderate

Table 6 presents the extent of problems in giving exercise and activities. It shows that 2 indicators are considered serious problems namely; the ability of learning guides and other references and availability of manipulative materials and other supplies.

Yara in his research entitled “Teaching/Learning Resources and Academic Performance in Mathematics in Secondary Schools in Bondo District of Kenya” he posited that out of the eight independent variables, only four were significant and could be used to predict academic performance in mathematics which are classroom, laboratories, stationeries and teaching aids. These findings are in consonance with the findings of Yadar in 2007 and the report by UNESCO in 2008 which opined that teaching/ learning materials such as textbooks, class rooms, teaching aids (chalk, board, ruler and protractor), stationeries and laboratories affect academic performance of the learners. Also the result of the findings agreed with that of Mutai in 2006 who asserted that learning is strengthened when there is enough reference materials such as textbooks, exercise books, teaching aids and class rooms while He further asserted that academic achievement illustrates per excellence the correct use of these materials (Qtd. in Yara).

The preparation of varied activities that will address diverse learners, fluency in the use of mother tongue and mastery of the standards and competencies are considered moderate problems. This means that there is a moderate problem encountered by the teachers in terms of giving exercises and activities as reflected on its weighted mean of 3.25.

Table 7. Class Performance of the Pupils in Mathematics

N = 56

Rating	Frequency	Percentage (%)
90 and above (Advanced)	1	1.79
85 - 89% (Proficient)	3	5.36
80– 84% (Approaching Proficiency)	27	48.21
75% - 79% (Developing)	23	41.07
74% and below (Beginning)	2	3.57
Average Performance	79.69 (Approaching Proficiency)	
Standard Deviation	3.73	

Table 7 shows the class performance of pupils in Mathematics for the School Year 2013-2014. It reveals the biggest group of 27 or 48.21% got the grades that range from 80-84% which means “Approaching Proficiency”. There are 23 classes or 41.07% got the grades that range from 75-79% which means “Developing”, 3 classes or 5.36% got the grades of 85-89% which means “Proficient”, 2 classes or 3.57% got the grades of 74% and below which means “Beginning” and 1 class or 1.79% got a grade of 90 and above which means “Advance”.

Results imply that the average performance of the pupils in class show that they have developed the fundamental knowledge and skills expected to be mastered and core understanding and with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers, and can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks.

The above finding conforms to that of Antiquina’s study. She also discloses that most of her respondents have a satisfactory rating of (80%-84%) and have an overall performance of 81.03% (36).

Table 8. Relationship Between the Extent of Problems Encountered by the Teachers and Their Pupils’ Academic Performance

Pupils’ Academic Performance and Teachers Extent of Problems Encountered in...	Computed r	Degree of Relationship
Translation of the Mathematical Concepts/Language	- 0.2328	Slight
Utilization of Effective Questioning Skill	- 0.1179	Negligible
Utilization of Effective Reacting Technique	- 0.1630	Negligible
Giving of Exercises and Activities	- 0.0786	Negligible
Overall	- 0.1671	Negligible

The data reveal that a “slight” relationship exists between the teachers’ extent of problems in translation of the Mathematical concepts or language and their pupils’ academic performance. The value of “r” indicates a negative sign. Hence, the finding means that as the problem of the teachers increases in this area, the lower is the academic performance of the pupils. As noted in Table 3, the teachers experienced a “serious” problem in the translation of Mathematical concepts or language. This finding was also in line with Gaarder (1985) in Bolaji where he argued that the use of English as the language of the test was one reason for low achievement scores in Hispanic students. Therefore with effective communication and translation of the mathematical concepts students stand a better chance to comprehend what is taught to them thereby making teaching more effective and result oriented.(Lassa)

On the other hand, the other areas like the extent of problems in utilization of effective questioning skill, reacting technique and giving of exercises and activities show a negligible relationship with the pupils’ academic performance. Generally, teachers experienced only a “moderate” problem in effective questioning skill and in giving exercises and activities while a “slight” problem in reacting technique as revealed in Tables 4, 5 and 6. These results may indicate that the degree of problems they encountered is manageable and they can find ways to overcome them in order not to affect the performance of the pupils.

Based on the study of Gregorio, the absolute value of a teacher is not in the regular performance of duties but rather in his power to lead and inspire his pupils through the influence of his wholesome personality and his resourcefulness to find solutions to the problems encountered in class. Love for the pupils, sympathy for their interests, tolerance, and a definite capacity for understanding results to effective teaching and learning (115).

Table 9. Relationship Between the Teachers’ Number of Relevant Trainings Attended and the Extent of Problems Encountered

Number of Relevant Trainings Attended and...	Computed r	Degree of Relationship
Translation of the Mathematical Concepts/Language	- 0.1293	Negligible
Utilization of Effective Questioning Skill	- 0.2529	Slight
Utilization of Effective Reacting Technique	- 0.2610	Slight
Giving of Exercises and Activities	- 0.2652	Slight
Overall	- 0.2838	Slight

The data reflect that a negligible relationship is seen between the number of relevant trainings attended by the teachers and their extent of problems encountered in translation of the mathematical concepts or language. The trainings that these teachers participated in for the last 3 years are all related to k-12. These trainings do not specifically discuss the competencies that the pupils will be learning. Teachers must learn these from themselves. It is also mentioned in the previous discussion that teachers experienced a “serious” problem in translation of the mathematical concepts or language. These might be the reasons why the number of trainings attended by the teachers does not establish a relationship to how they translate the mathematical concepts or language. Briars observes that any reform in the curriculum especially Mathematics requires that teachers be reoriented towards mother tongue language in teaching and learning that ensures that a teacher in every classroom engages the pupils that ensures high level achievement. However, the data show a “slight” relationship between the relevant trainings attended and the extent of problems they encounter in the following: utilization of effective questioning skill, utilization of effective reacting technique and giving of exercises and activities. The relationship is noted to be inversely proportional. This means that the lesser the number of trainings they attended, the more problems they experienced in the following: utilization of effective questioning skill, reacting technique and giving of exercises and activities. This happens because the time teachers spend in professional development makes a difference in their classroom instruction most especially when the activities focus on high-quality subject-matter content. Extended opportunities to better understand student learning, curriculum materials and instruction, and subject-matter content can boost the performance of both teachers and students. Generally, a negative “slight” relationship is revealed if all problems are combined. Finally, according to Kelly, to provide new teachers with the greatest chance of success, they need to have completed a teacher preparation program that provides them with knowledge, experience, and guidance in their profession (2).

Table 10. Relationship Between the Teachers’ Educational Attainment and the Extent of Problems Encountered

Teachers’ Educational Attainment and...	Computed r	Degree of Relationship
Translation of the Mathematical Concepts/Language	- 0.1316	Negligible
Utilization of Effective Questioning Skill	- 0.1607	Negligible
Utilization of Effective Reacting Technique	- 0.2396	Slight
Giving of Exercises and Activities	- 0.2478	Slight
Overall	- 0.2422	Slight

The curriculum in the graduate studies has been used for over a decade and might not include specific areas on how the K-12 must be implemented especially in the following areas: translation of the mathematical concepts/language and utilization of effective questioning skill with the use of mother tongue. Therefore, the educational attainment of the teachers is not considered as a determinant on these areas. Moreover, the Teacher Education Institutions (TEI) where these teacher respondents graduated didn’t have a subject that hones the skills of these teachers.

However, a “slight” negative relationship is established between their educational attainment and the following: utilization of effective reacting technique and giving of exercises and activities. The negative sign indicates that the lower the educational attainment of the teachers, the higher is the problems that they encountered on the mentioned areas. The graduate studies have subjects that focus on classroom strategies and these might help the teachers in imparting the mother tongue instruction.

As Reymunds stressed, effectiveness and initiative in teaching and assessing pupil’s performance depended largely on teacher qualification.

Table 11. Relationship Between the Teachers’ Length of Teaching Experience and the Extent of Problems Encountered

Length of Teaching Experience and...	Computed r	Degree of Relationship
Translation of the Mathematical Concepts/ Language	- 0.0800	Negligible
Utilization of Effective Questioning Skill	- 0.0899	Negligible
Utilization of Effective Reacting Technique	- 0.0164	Negligible
Giving of Exercises and Activities	- 0.0197	Negligible
Overall	- 0.0689	Negligible

The data illustrate that there is no relationship between the length of teaching experience of the teachers and the extent of problems they encountered in the following areas: translation of the mathematical concepts/language, utilization of effective questioning skill, utilization of effective reacting technique and giving of exercises and activities. The K-12 curriculum is new and has been implemented for the last 3 years. Thus the length of teachers’ experience is not considered as a contributory to teachers’ extent of problems encountered in classroom instruction. This means that teachers experience the same level of problems in the classroom instruction using the mother tongue regardless of how long they have been teaching the subject.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In the light of the findings of this study, the following conclusions are hereby drawn.

1. Majority of the teachers are non-master’s degree holders and been in the teaching profession for a longer time. Most of them attended the indicated seminar-workshops related to k-12 instruction but only once.
2. The teachers encountered a “serious” problem in translation of Mathematical concepts or language to the pupils and a “moderate” problem in utilization of effective questioning skill and in giving exercises and activities. Moreover, they also “slightly” had a problem in utilization of effective reactive technique.
3. The class performance of the pupils was in the “approaching proficiency” level. However, a significant percentage of them were still in the developing and beginning levels.
4. There was a “slight” negative relationship between the extent of problems encountered by the teachers in translation of the Mathematical concepts and the pupils’ academic performance.
5.
 - a. There was a “slight” negative relationship between the number of relevant training attended by the teachers and the following variables: utilization of effective questioning skill, utilization of effective reacting technique and giving of exercises and activities.
 - b. There was a “slight” negative relationship between the educational attainment of the teachers and the following variables: utilization of effective reacting technique and giving of exercises and activities.

In general, the Grade 1 teachers encountered a “serious” problem in the translation of Mathematical concepts or language to the pupils and this was inversely related to the pupils’ academic performance. The more problems that the teachers encountered on this area, the lower were the academic performance of the pupils.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

In the light of the findings and conclusions drawn, the following recommendations were suggested:

1. Teachers should upgrade their one’s professional skills by pursuing further studies and attend more trainings focusing on the translation of the content of the competencies in mother tongue.
2. Teachers in coordination with the Division Math Supervisor should formulate varied exercises and activities in Mother tongue so as to enhance learning.

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II. To what extent are the problems met in the teaching of Mathematics using Mother Tongue?

Direction: Please indicate the extent to which you have encountered the following problems using the scale below as guide in answering the question.

Scale	Verbal Description	Explanation
5	Very Serious Problem	The problem is encountered by the teachers 81 -100% of the time.
4	Serious Problem	The problem is encountered by the teachers 61-80% of the time.
3	Moderate Problem	The problem is encountered by the teachers 41 – 60% of the time.
2	Slight Problem	The problem is encountered by the teachers 21 – 40% of the time
1	Not a Problem	The problem is encountered by the teachers 1 -20% of the time.

A. Translation of the Mathematical Concepts/Language

Extent of Problems in Translating significant mathematical terms in Mother Tongue in the following competencies:	Very Serious Problem	Serious Problem	Moderate Problem	Slight Problem	Not a Problem
1. Composes and decomposes a given number <i>Ex. 9 – 4 ug 5, 5 ug 4, 6 ug 3</i>					
2. Reads and writes numbers up to 100 in symbols and in words <i>Ex. 31 - trayenta i -uno</i>					
3. Renames numbers into tens and ones <i>Ex. 78 – 7 tagnapulo 8 tinagus-a</i>					
4. Recognizes and compares coins and bills up to PhP100 and their notations <i>Ex. 5 kasingkopisosugbayentepisos</i>					
5. Visualizes and adds numbers with sums through 99 without or with regrouping <i>Ex. 25+47</i>					
6. Uses the expanded form to explain subtraction with regrouping <i>Ex. 50 + 4</i> <u> 28 + 8</u>					
7. Counts groups of equal quantity using concrete objects up to 50 and writes an equivalent expression. <i>Ex. 2 groups of 5</i>					
8. Compares and classifies 2-dimensional (flat/plane) and 3 dimensional(solid) figures according to common attributes <i>Ex. Nawongsakono, rectangular ngakarton, cylinder</i>					
9. Constructs equivalent number expression using addition and subtraction. <i>Ex. 6+5 = 12 -1</i>					
10. Estimate and measure capacity using non-standard unit <i>Ex. Si Nene nagkinahanglanug 30 kabasosa alangsayangnatawhan.</i>					

<i>angusakapitselmosulodug 5 kabasongajuice man kapitselsa juice angiyangandamon.</i>					
11. Solves problems involving time. <i>Ex. Ika-walokataknaugnapulog lima</i>					
12. Infers and interprets data presented in a pictograph without scales <i>Ex .Unsakabahinang pictograph?</i>					

Utilization of Effective Questioning Skill

Extent of Problems in Utilizing Effective Questioning Skills in Class Interaction	Very Serious Problem	Serious Problem	Moderate Problem	Slight Problem	Not a Problem
1. Ability to ask varied type of question					
2. Ability to direct the question to all pupils.					
3. Ability to call on non-volunteer pupils.					
4. Ability to rephrase questions that are unclear to the pupils.					
5. Ability to ask related questions one from simple to complex one after another.					
6. Ability to ask questions that require abstract thinking.					
7. Ability to ask questions that develop higher order thinking skills.					
8. Ability to provide for sufficient wait time for the pupils to answer.					
9. Ability to assess Comprehension					
10. Ability to involve in the discussion as many pupils as possible					

Source: SEAMEO INNOTECH. (1994)*The Interactive Instruction Series for Teacher Education*, p. 28

B. Utilization of Effective Reacting Technique

Extent of Problems in Utilizing effective reacting technique in handling pupils responses during class interaction	Very Serious Problem	Serious Problem	Moderate Problem	Slight Problem	Not a Problem
1. Ability to provide feedback on the correctness or incorrectness of a response					
2. Ability to give appropriate praise to high quality responses					
3. Ability to make follow up questions					
4. Ability to redirect questions to other pupils					
5. Ability to follow up a pupil's response with related question					
6. Ability to re-phrasing the seemingly unclear question					
7. Ability to show non – verbal encouragement					
8. Ability to encourage learners to ask questions					

Source: SEAMEO INNOTECH. *The Interactive Instruction Series for Teacher Education, Trainor's Manual on the Art of Questioning and Reacting Techniques*, 1994)

C. Giving of Exercises and Activities

Extent of problems met in giving exercises /activities using mother tongue	Very Serious Problem	Serious Problem	Moderate Problem	Slight Problem	Not a Problem
1. Availability of learning guides and other references					
2. Varied activities prepared that will address diverse learners					
3. Availability of manipulative materials and other supplies/materials					
4. Fluency in the use of the mother tongue					
5. Mastery of the standards and competencies					

III. What is the average final rating of your pupils in Mathematics for SY 2013-2014?

IV. Comments/Suggestions

